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BRIDGING THE PAST AND THE PRESENT THROUGH FESTIVAL PERFORMANCES: THE EXAMPLE OF THE *OGANI* FESTIVAL CELEBRATION AT IDAH.

Emmy Unuja Idegu,

Introduction

The past of a people, and the understanding of that past, assist in the easy comprehension of the present and a projection into their future. One of the ways that the past of Africans has been kept alive for centuries is through indigenous festival performances. Not even our contact with foreign cultures during the colonial and even post-colonial era could totally obliterate this important position festivals occupy to the African. This paper attempts to take a look at the *Ogani* festival celebration by the *Angwa* people in Idah, Kogi State as a potent medium of re-telling and retaining the past of the Igala people and how that past bears relevance to their today.

Festivals comprise a variety of forms, from the most spectacular to the most secretive and emotionally charged. Festival performances remain one of the most important aspects of the African culture through which the people's belief system and ways of life are expressed. As Wole Soyinka in Olaniyan. R (ed) (1982:241) asserts.

The persistent habit of dismissing festivals as belonging to a spontaneous inartistic expression of community demands reexamination. The level of organization involved, the integration, the

sublime with the mundane, the endowment of the familiar with properties of the unique, all indicate that it is into the heart of man's instinct and need... as it is most comprehensive and community involving.

This unique and important unifying role of festivals is also a reason why festival performances are so cherished in Africa. Every society has its own peculiar norms which not only characterize it, but which determine the life of its members. Thus, in traditional African societies, this role is played by festivals and ritual performances. E.P. Modum in Kalu U. O. (ed) (1978:46) observes that,

.. the social and moral life in African traditional societies should be seen to be organized around festive manifestation which fulfill the function of social and moral control as well as provide entertainment and direction. These ceremonies are therefore important as indicators of group interests and values and various aspects of social life.

Through festival performances the community life of any given people in Africa is-sharpened; invigorated, and policed. The people's past is brought to bear through festivals and their contemporary relevance is appraised for communal living and cohesion.

It is within this understanding of communal involvement and solidarity through festivals that E. N. Obiechina in Kalu U.O. (ed) (1978:268) records that,

Large-scale festivals, whether of arts, culture or sports are not new in the world. From very remote antiquity, history, race, civilization, nationality or religion, have made a point of coming together, periodically, to express their sense of communion through those things which have given them their feeling of unity, those things which not only defined their unique relatedness, but also distinguished them from all other peoples.

In as much as festival performance brings people together, it draws some mark of difference between one group of people and the other. The identity of a people can to an extent be defined by their festival performances. Through festivals, people have access to expressing their inner beliefs in religion, and by singing and dancing they make their physical bodies participate emphatically in the worship or reverence to the gods and ancestors.

This is made possible when a people have come to accept a festival as their collectively owned medium of expressing themselves, and a way also of creating meanings to existence that is acceptable to all within that community, it is in line with this assertion that Kwame Gyekye (1997:107) asserts that in such festivals, "meanings have become homogenized and can thus be said to be generally shared by all the citizens whose basic values are cherished and considered as constituting the social context within which they spontaneously feel they belong, which they regard as theirs and in the appreciation and enjoyment of whose products they all participate". In the **Ogani** festival performance is therefore the sum total, as it were, of the life or the ways of life of the Angwa people at Idah.

Praying, for instance, holds a significant position in **Ogani** festival. Quite a number of them have been handed down through the generations, while others are always created as the occasions arise and or demand. Praying tradition is very much firmly noted in Igala society. Prayers offered during the **Ogani** festival have familiar forms which clearly indicate that they have been used repeatedly for many years. As J.S. Mbiti (1975:1) will have it,

...the themes covered in these prayers are almost timeless... and it would be reasonable, therefore, to guess that people have for dozens of centuries prayed for the same thing.

These would include prayers for recovery from illness; protection against danger, for prosperity and success, offspring and rain. Though the exact or original wordings do change from time to time, the needs which have occasioned the prayers, as well as the contents of most of the prayers, have not changed considerably through the ages.

Music remains a crucial aspect of the **Ogani** festival in Idah. The entire community at large participates in this music making. Even when certain areas are extremely difficult and can only be well executed by specially trained artistes, there are other aspects that are simple enough for the average member of the community to join in. A good example is an instance where the solo part of the song is performed by trained **Ogani** soloists, while the choral part may be sung by any member of the community who is either stimulated or cares to join.

Close to music is the issue of satire during the **Ogani** songs rendition, every area of life provides material for the **Ogani** satirist and there is hardly any personality, no matter how highly placed, that the **Ogani** singer cannot adore, lampoon or ridicule in his songs. D. I. Nwoga in Abalogu. N. U. fed) (1981:233) explains the place of satire in any society when he views that.

.. .harmony between people and between the people and their world requires an exact observance of these customs. Failure to follow the practice in any area of life, especially with regard to the moral code, immediately invites satire, so that there are satires against men and women for various failures like promiscuity, stealing, a man not looking after his wife, laziness in women and men. Even political

leadership has its moral code of reciprocity; so that there are satires against selfish politicians who fail to provide for their people.

This way, the **Ogani** performer is active in his role as the regulator of social behaviours of the Angwa settlers at Idah.

Historical background of *Ogani* festival in Idah

The **Ogani** festival has its historical beginning in the Igala war of independence from the Jukuns dated 1449. The Igala people in present day Kogi State were a vassal kingdom to the Jukuns (in present day Taraba state) until there came one Ata Igala (the Igala king) by the name, Idoko, who saw no reason whatsoever, why this oppression should continue. So he led his people against the Jukun forces. To achieve the breakaway, Idoko, with what equates Wole Soyinka's thesis of the "Ogunian Will", instead of sending grains, cowries, and animals as tribute, sent dirt like human faeces, rotten animals, dead birds and skeletons, to the Aku Uka of Wukari, (the Jukun king) with a defiant message that he would no longer pay tribute to him. Idoko's "tribute" was an insult to the Aku, who, after due consultations with his councilors and war generals, got ready his army to crush the Igala rebellion.

If the Aku won the war, it would mark absolute loyalty of the Igala race to the Jukuns, but he lost, the Ata Igala would gain independence for his people from the Aku Uka government. The war was from both sides, a decisive one. Idoko sought the will of the ancestors through the *Ifa* medium of communication and certain sacrifices were performed which involved the life of one of the Ata's children, Princess Om'odoko. The sacrifices were carried on as ordered by the river Inachailo bank, about three kilometers from Ida'n town on the idah - Nsukka road, and the route of the Jukun forces to idah. Added to this sacrifice, some islamic scholars were invited from Be'beji village in Kano to offer prayers for the

Igala to triumph in the war. Oral tradition has it that one Mallam

Aliyu Bebeji led the team of moslems from Bebeji to Idah for this assignment. They offered prayers for some days and finally climaxed the process with the revelation to poison Inachallo River where the Jukun warriors were to camp.

On arrival, the Jukun caught and ate fishes from the Inachallo river and drank of the water. This resulted in an outbreak of cholera in their camp. Many of them died while a few survived to fight the battle. At sunrise the next day, the igaia troops arrived at the Idah side of the Inachallo river whiie the enemies were on the Nsukka side. Determined to win the war, they attacked the remaining soldiers of the Aku and massacred them en masse. The Aku of Wukari was made to renounce all claims in Igalaland and Idoko from then ruled as an independent king and so have the other Atas after him.

Because of their assistance in the war and the subsequent victory of the Igala people, the Ata Igaia offered the Hausa Mallams a hand of friendship that they should continue to reside with him. Their first settlement was at Igecneba, an outskirts of Idah but he later gave them an alternative settlement. Being traders, the mallams opted for the eastern part of the town toward Igboland, where they could continue their commercial activities. They finally settled at a distance from the Inachallo river, a settlement which has the Hausa word *Angiva*. This was the first settlement of Moslems in Igalaland, and from where islamic religion is said to have spread to other parts of the Igala kingdom.

The Mallams later intimated the Ata Igala of a victory commemorating festival they used to perform while at Bebeji and which they wished to celebrate to mark this historic victory and to remind future generations of the event. Their request was willingly-granted, hence the birth and commencement of *Ogani* festival at Idah and the first of its kind in igalaland. The historic background

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of this important annual festival performed by the *Angwa* people of Idah can therefore be traced as far back as the said war. The *Ogani* festival became an important annual cultural festival in Igalaland to commemorate Igala victory in their war of independence from the Jukun. The festival performance, as a product of history is similar to what Yaro-Gella in G.G Darah(ed) (1993:12) tags historical consciousness, "a consciousness about one's identity historically determined: a process informed by a clear vision of love and understanding of the past as well as pride in what you are, who you are and what you can be. derived from a conscious knowledge of the past". Over the years, the festival has always been held in the fourth month of the year, Aprii. Since it is an entirely *Angwa* settlers' festival, elders of *Angwa* are summoned together by the Imam of *Angwa* called the *Akpochi*. This office is usually reserved for the oldest man in the *Akpochi* lineage.

Six main clans constitute the descendants of the Hausa Mallams from Bebeji-Kano, settled at *Angwa*, Idah. They are the *Adache*, *Am'ata*, *Am'awo*, *Adamihia*, *Obukele* and *Okomanyi*. Added to these are some fifteen clans. They are the *Oweye*, *Okutubi*, *Ebutu*, *Om'odoko*, *Otete*, *Adamede* clans. Others are the *Aka*, *Adumale*, *Oliaja*, *Eja*, *Ohiado*, *Akpochi*, *Olimanu* and the *Ochala* clans. Elders of these clans meet to decide on the days of *Ogani* performance. The accepted date is communicated to the Ata Igala through the *Ohiado* who is the intermediary between the *Angwa* people and the Ata.

The all-night performance

The first day (eve of the full *Ogani* display) records an all-night performance when people from various parts of the country, assemble at *Angwa* according to their clan to eat, drink, dance

and rejoice as a prelude to the activities of the following day. The all-night activities are of significance because the spirits of the people are prepared for the show the following day. Locally brewed wine, palm wine and beer are offered with food. In the context of the festival, food and drink are strongly believed to have mystical links between man and his fellow man and also between man and the “spiritual realities/” Food here does not only provide nourishment for the up-keep of the individual, but also sustains relationships between people and the spiritual realm. The relationship between people and the living- dead is renewed through man’s offerings of food and drinks which are symbols of remembrance and welcome, since the departed continue to be present with the living.

The U’kafu

Very early in the morning, all the interested male descendants of *Angwa* disappear one by one into the bush to meet at a given place where they are made-up for the main performance. U’kafu here means to make-up. Make-up is applied on their cleanly shaven heads, faces, and the lower part of their arms and legs. Female descendants of *Angwa* do not show up at *U’kafu*. It is exclusively the male descendants who are allowed here. Exclusion of women from such places of performance in Igala traditional festivals is not unconnected with “impure” condition of women at certain times of the month when they menstruate. Their participation in *U’kafu* is considered to pollute the purity they seek. The *U’kafu* visit marks one of the sacred points of the *Ogani* festival, hence, the exclusion of the women. Out of the many people that go to *U’kafu*, only fifteen are selected to perform the *Ogani* display on return to *Angwa*.

This alienation in *U’kafu* is not strange an act in African traditional festivals. Tom A. Miacht, (1980:8) explains that “a

society is said to be- "closed" so far as, and to the extent that, within the range of its subjective meaning and the validity of its authority, the purification of certain persons is excluded, limited or subject to conditions." The prerogative of *U'kafu* activities rests only on the *amomenekele* (male descendants) of *Angwa*.

At *U'kafu*, all people present, stay in groups according to their clan, with the activities being overseen by the clan leader. Each performer has a pair of horns, large and costly costume called **Obo**, tied with two bells to the waist. The horns are those of dreaded forest animals; a sign of bravery by their fore-fathers to have killed such animals. This bravery is part of what they now celebrate yearly. The fearful look and use of horns are believed to frighten evil forces from the land.

Life to the *Ogani* performance is not confined to its physical form alone; it transcends the human boundary into the spiritual realm. The departed are therefore, thought to be still alive, even if in a form totally different from the human beings. A visit to *U'kafu*, and by implications, a "visit" to the ancestors, is very necessary because, as J.S. Mbiti (1975:102) observes "to forget the living-dead would upset the harmony of life, it would generate ill-health, failure in hunting, difficult child birth, and other evils. Normalizing relations with the departed ensures continued peace and tranquility in the daily affairs of human life." The traditional African believes strongly in the existence of a being whose wishes he must conform with and whose experience he must emulate. In other words, he accepts that his existence in the world has a spiritual dimension that there is some kind of force which determines, as it were, the sense of his life and that he cannot afford to ignore this force. The traditional Igaia visualizes life and the world as a whole in the context of his relationship with the sacred realm. More precisely, the essence and continuation of social life are guaranteed through well determined and periodical

contacts with the deities during which the society renews its faith in the gods. This is what the *Ogani* performers do during their trip and stay at *U'kafu*.

Returning from *U'kafu* to *Angwa*, each of the fifteen costumed and made-up *Ogani* performers has a little bunch of leaves in his mouth, closed tight enough to disallow the removal of the leaves, signifying that from that point till they arrive at *Angwa*, there is no talking to each other. Also, on no account must one performer's leg touch the other, and there is no looking or turning back. It is believed that while leaving *U'kafu*, they are escorted out to *Angwa* by the spirits of the ancestors, and there is no need to look back at them since there is nothing to fear from behind them. The fifteen performers go into *Angwa* from *U'kafu*, running, chasing invisible evil spirits; they scatter about in their chase then re-unite in procession, led by the eldest of the fifteen clans (*Adache*). till they arrive at *Er'ojo*.

Performance at Er'ojo (Ogani Adache)

When the performers go to *U'kafu*. it is time for the all-night revelers to take a break only to reappear some four hours later when the fourth stage of the festival starts. Music climaxes when the fifteen *Obos* are sighted at a distance from *Er'ojo*. Their sight is greeted with a very loud ovation. They respond by jumping up high, each with his pair of horns and mouth still "sealed" with leaves. At a point, all of them come together, forming a circle, piercing the ground purposely with their horns, which symbolically indicate pinning down their defeated foe. They then scatter to drive people here and there as they pursue evil spirits out of town.

The fifteen *Obos* perform here and according to their clan and seniority. *Obo Adache* begins the performance and it proceeds in the following order: *Adache* (Oweye clan). *Am'ata* (Okutubi clan), *Am'awo* (Ebutu cian), *Adamihia* (Utoko cian).

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Obukele (Omodoko dan), Okomanyi (Otete dan), Adamede (Oweye dan), Aka (Oweye dan), Adumafe (Oweye dan), Oliaja (Oweye dan), Eja (Utoko dan), Oniado (Oweye dan), Akpochi (Om'odoko dan), Olimamu (Utoko dan), Ochala (Utoko dan). The *Obos* do not dance, thus, music does not come up during this display. Whenever an Obo is performing, the spectators shout loud *Aye! Aye!"Aye! Aye!*, as the *Obo* side tumbles fast to the right hand side, then to the left, as many times as he can and as fast as possible. He holds his pair of horns very high, which during this display, must not either fall or even mistakenly touch the ground. No ill omen surpasses this during the *Ogani* festival. If an *Obo's* horn falls, it is believed that he will not survive the year.

Ogani Obo acrobatic show is very impossible without consummate skill, resulting from hard work and talent. On completion of this performance at *Erojo*, the fifteen *Obos* move from each clan head to the other, followed by the spectators as they display, starting from *Ohiado* sub-clan of *Oweye*, as the nearest place to the *Er'oyo* display ground. This performance is called the *Ogani Adache*. It begins right from the dressing and returning of the *Obos* from *Uk'afu* and terminates at Ategune, a distance from *Er'oyo*, where *Ogani Ohiado* commences.

The Ogani Ohiado

The *Ogani* performers are led by the *Obo Ohiado* from Ategune to the Ata Igala's palace. Music groups lead the procession to the palace before the arrival of the *Ogani Ohiado* performers. While music, songs and dance continue, insults aimed at the audience are woven into the lyrics of the songs. Interestingly, this does not demand response or negative reaction from the happy crowd. Insults that on ordinary days will cause some fracas are seen as

harmless this day. Any spectator so attacked, sees it as a sign to correct his mistakes thereafter.

The *Ogani* festival marks and celebrates the victory of the Igala people over the Jukuns. Hence, during the procession, solemn chants of praise and of victory punctuate the revei songs, thanking their ancestors. People move during this procession gladly recalling the defeat of the Jukuns, saying with pride what equates J. S. Mbiti's (1975:58) comments.

We have winnowed them as the chaff which falls from the basket, as the chaff is carried by the wind are they driven this way and that, we returned victorious, our enemies are scattered. It is well. There are fears and lamentation in their villages; there is lamentation for their young men that are dead, for their young men who our spears caused to stumble. Their wives are widowed and their daughters are fatherless; there is sorrow for the empty hofhesteads that are silent, spirits of our fathers, we greet you.

This is a moment of great rejoicing during which their ancestors are thanked for this victory and called upon for protection. "We adjure you, help us our fathers and it is well" they pray. At the end of the performance here, the Ata retreats to his palace after which the *Obos* go back to *Angwa*, ending the breathtaking acrobatic display by the *Ogani* performers.

The *Ogani* *Ochala*

Ogani Ohiado ends the display by tfw *Obos* in the *Ogani* festival. Till the festival ends, it is prayers galore, begun by the *Ogani Ochala*. Right from *Angwa*, through *Er'ojo* to the Ata Igala's palace, the *Ochala*, dressed in Islamic attire of gown and cap with turban, leads a group of men and women (also dressed like him) in prayers. Drums are solemnly beaten; definitely not for

dance, but for spiritual upliftment. No gong is beaten by any dance group as everywhere is still.

On arrival at the entrance to the palace, the *Ochala* kneels, followed by all *Ogani Ochala* members in a very long queue to offer prayers, counting their chaplets. They rise and go round the

palace three times with one of the women carrying a very long sword. The display of this ancient sword signifies a mark of war and victory of the Igala people. The fact that this sword is carried by a woman goes a long way to show the importance of women in Igala wars of independence. The sacrifice of princess Inikpi that guaranteed victory for the Igala during the Igala-Bini war attests to this importance. So also can one say of the sacrifice of princess Omodoko during the Igala-Jukun war.

At the end of the third and final round of prayers round the palace, they go straight back to *Angwa*, praying on their way to end the spectacular aspects of the festival celebration and leaving one more stage to end the *Ogani* festival performance.

The Ogani Akpochi

The *Ogani Akpochi* usually begins at about 9.p.m. with few or no spectators at all. The time of this part of the festival and its less spectacular display, force spectators back to their houses, for after all, no one can be very sure of what lies in darkness. *Ogani Akpochi*, staged by only very aged men, is meant to ask the ancestors for a good night and acceptance of all they had done in the day. Like the *Ogani Ochala*, they too pray round the palace three times as they chant, *LA'ILA HA'ILALLAHU* (There is no other god but Allah). At the end of their "journey" round the palace, the *Ogani Akpochi* group is offered some gifts by the Ata Igala, represented by the *Ohiegba*, the traditional liaison officer and one of the principal eunuchs to the Ata Igala. He

officiates for the Ata and presents them gifts of *Obi mele* (four kolanuts), *Oko icham icham nyogwoko* (1,000 cowries, today's equivalent amount given them is four kobo), *aiko fufu ako nwojo* (spotless white cockerel) *ugbogbo* (a piece of white cloth). These are offered in recognition and appreciation of the *Ogani* festival performers; that is the *Angwa* people. They also provide the context against which the people's needs may be enumerated. These are symbolized in the white cockerel (life), white piece of cloth (peace), four kobo (material prosperity), and four kola-nuts (food and the giving spirit).

The *Ogani Akpochi*, marks the end of the *Ogani* celebrations at Idah. The *Ogani Angwa* festival can therefore, be said to be an annual spiritual environmental sanitation exercise, during which period the people's shortcomings are corrected and their needs made known to their ancestors. The festival also cements unity amongst the people for peaceful co-existence of the humans and contact with the spiritual realities.

Conclusion.

Since the victory of the Igala people in the Igaia-Jukun war of 1449, the *Ogani* festival has remained an important festival that commemorates the "independence" of the Igala people from the Jukuns. The festival keeps fresh in people's minds their past historic and cultural values, and also the first cultural contact of the Igala people with the Hausas which is being maintained till date. The significance of the *Ogani* festival is made more glaring as it assumes a structure of collective mobilization. As the isolated and incipient emotional responses of single individuals are pulled and collectively directed through the *Ogani* performance, the sum total of the performer's and the community's cultural values and societal norms are evaluated, re-appraised and communally accepted. The characteristic features of the festival can thus, be

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summed up to include a marked desire of the living and the ancestors to relate by means of musical performances, dances, and prayers. Through this the community ensures the continuity of its existence.

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